

Do Surgeons Forget? Investigating the Impact of Days out of Practice on Health Outcomes for Emergency Hip Fracture Patients

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Learning-by-doing has been the object of a large literature in economics. A potential determinant of learning is the frequency of practice.

This study's objective is to understand how the time elapsed between surgeries affects a surgeon's performance in the context of hip fracture surgery. Hip fracture is a complex and high-volume condition, involving often multi-comorbid and frail patients.

Methods: The dataset comprises detailed patient-level hospital administrative data for all emergency hip fracture patients admitted in England between 2008 and 2016, corresponding to a panel dataset of over 2,000 orthopaedic surgeons. Post-surgery health outcomes are measured using patients' 30-day mortality rate.

Using a fixed effects model, I explore whether the number of days elapsed between two hip fracture cases have an impact on a surgeon's outcomes, controlling for a rich set of patients' clinical and socio-economic factors (age, gender, ethnicity, comorbidities, socio-economic deprivation, weekend day dummy, pre-surgery length of stay). Surgeon fixed effects account for time-constant unobserved heterogeneity in surgeon quality. Interacted hospital-year dummies further control for potential confounders linked to hospital-specific changes in medical equipment or hospital heterogeneity in adaptation of national clinical guidelines over time.

Results: Results show that time interruptions in practice do not have a causal negative effect on health outcomes, suggesting that skills do not depreciate with interruptions in practice in hip fracture.

The effect of temporal distance may be offset by a high level of repetition (high-volumes) prior to the break. Further analyses show no evidence of heterogeneity of results by surgeons' volume and share of activity in hip fracture.

Findings however suggest that less frequent practice may be beneficial. Average health outcomes improve with breaks between 15 and 45 days by around 0.4 percentage points (six percent relative effect), compared to everyday practice. Analyses show that these effects are not explained by differences in treatment choice or post-surgical length of stay, ruling these out as mediating factors.

Discussion: Patients break their proximal femur, often following a fall, and need to be treated within 48 hours of admission to the closest hospital. This study exploits the plausibly exogenous variation volumes and timings of hip fracture admissions to contribute to the scarce causal evidence on the effect of time breaks on health outcomes and general understanding of surgeons' learning process.